

(DNOX), and 5-amino-8-hydroxyquinoline dihydrochloride (Am.Ox), by potentiometric technique. Complexation of many rare earth ions with ligands OX, OSA and IOSA in aqueous media have been reported¹. The present ligands have been chosen to see the effect of substituents on stability of the Nd^{III} complexes.

Experimental

A stock solution (0.02 M) of NdCl₃.xH₂O (IREDA, Bombay) was prepared in calculated quantity of perchloric acid to prevent hydrolysis. The metal content was estimated complexometrically with EDTA using bromopyrogallol red as indicator². Stock solution (0.005 M) of all the ligands were prepared in 80% (v/v) purified dioxan-water media. OX (B.D.H.), OSA (E. Merck), and IDSA (B.D.H.) were commercially available. NtOX, NsOX, DNOX and AmOX were synthesised by known methods³. The experimental findings on melting point and nitrogen estimations and ir frequencies of the ligands were in accord with literature values⁴. Solutions of carbon dioxide-free NaOH (Merck) and 0.4 M perchloric acid (Riedel) were prepared and standardised potentiometrically. Stock solution of sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was prepared in double-distilled water.

In the potentiometric titration procedure, 4.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand containing 0.02 M perchloric acid in the absence and in the presence of 1.0 × 10⁻³ M metal was taken in 75% (v/v) dioxan-water media having a constant ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO₄). Hydrogen ion concentration in dioxan-water media was calculated by the method of Van Uitert and Haas⁵. The constants were evaluated by various computational methods⁶. Refined values of the constants are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND Nd^{III}-LIGAND CONSTANT IN 75% (v/v) DIOXAN-WATER MEDIUM

Temp. = 25°, Ionic strength (μ) = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand	Proton-Ligand constant		Nd ^{III} -Ligand constant		
	pK ₁ ^H	pK ₂ ^H	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃
OX	11.42	3.51	8.45	7.32	4.31
OSA	10.52	4.05	8.41	6.87	4.15
IOSA	8.96	2.50	7.34	5.12	4.32
NtOX	7.43	—	6.23	4.89	—
NsOX	7.22	—	4.02	3.52	—
DNOX	5.75	—	6.18	5.62	—
AmOX	10.20	—	8.27	6.64	—

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric study revealed the ligands OX, OSA and IOSA as biprotic and the ligands NtOX, NsOX, DNOX and AmOX as monoprotic. For complexation of Nd^{III} with OX, OSA, IOSA and AmOX, the values of $\bar{n}$ extended from 0 to 3, indicating the formation of three stepwise (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) complexes. Whereas in case of NtOX, NsOX and

DNOX, the $\bar{n}$ values extended from 0 to 2, indicating the formation of (1 : 1 and 1 : 2) complexes. Hydrolysis of [Nd^{III}-(OX)₃] complex was observed at pH 10.2, while those with NtOX, NsOX and DNOX were observed at pH 7.0. The trend in the stability of Nd^{III} complexes were in the ligand order, OX > OSA > AmOX > IOSA > NtOX > DNOX > NsOX, which is mostly in the order of decreasing ligand basicity (Table 1). In case of OX, OSA and IOSA, the substitution of SO₃H group and further addition of iodo group in parent OX analogue decrease the stability of complexes due to electron withdrawing properties of the added groups.

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Formation Constants of Lanthanide Complexes with some Amino Acids

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THE present paper describes a pH-metric study for the determination of formation constants of the La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} complexes with glycine, α-alanine, leucine or isoleucine.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Solutions for the equilibrium study were prepared in conductivity water. Free acid and metal contents of metal nitrate solutions were determined by acid-base² and complexometric³ methods.

Three sets of solutions containing (i) known amount of free HClO₄, (ii) solution (i) + known amount of ligand and (iii) solution (ii) + known

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LANTHANIDE COMPLEXES WITH AMINO ACIDS

Temp. = 25°, Ionic strength = 0.2 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand	Formation constant*	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}	Gd ^{III}
Glycine	log K_1	4.09	4.42	4.40	4.50	5.14	4.64
	log K_2	3.49	3.52	3.74	4.12	4.34	4.53
α -Alanine	log K_1	3.76	4.29	4.57	4.80	5.10	5.18
	log K_2	3.43	3.49	4.00	3.60	4.09	4.23
Leucine	log K_1	4.59	5.03	5.25	4.93	5.39	5.21
	log K_2	4.04	3.91	4.23	3.75	3.99	4.31
Isoleucine	log K_1	4.22	5.48	4.93	5.24	5.35	5.21
	log K_2	3.52	3.77	4.06	3.99	4.37	4.60

* limits of error, $\pm 0.02 - 0.09$ in log scale.

amount of metal nitrate, were prepared. Total volume of each solution was 50 ml. All the solutions were pH-metrically titrated with a standard 0.2 M NaOH solution using a Elico LI-10 G pH meter at 25°. From the titration data $\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated as described earlier⁴. Metal-ligand formation constants were calculated by the procedure of Irving-Rossotti^{5,6}. Results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The formation constants of trivalent lanthanide-amino acid complexes were found to be in the order, La < Ce < Pr < Nd < Sm > Gd. Steady increase in log K_1 values from La^{III} to Sm^{III} is the result of decrease of size of the M³⁺ ions with subsequent increase in ionic potential. The decrease in ionic size of lanthanide ions is not regular, the biggest decrease is being observed with the first electron added to each orbital *i.e.* in cases of Ce^{III}, Pr^{III} and Nd^{III}. Besides this, the charge-size ratio also increases from La^{III} to Gd^{III}. It is observed that higher the values of charge-size ratio, greater is the stability of the complexes.

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Equilibrium Studies on the Formation of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Mercury(II) in Solution

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MERCURY(II) compounds possess varying degree of toxicity^{1,2}. The toxic behaviour of the complexes besides other factors is probably dependent on the stability and geometry of the various complex species. The literature survey indicates extensive research work on the determination of stability of binary complexes especially with amines, amino acids and sulphur containing ligands³. However, similar investigations on mixed ligand complexes are less comprehensive^{4,5}, and only a few ternary systems have been studied.

Equilibrium studies on the following MAL type complexes of Hg^{II} have been carried out: A. (i) Hg^{II}Cl-dien; B. (i) Hg^{II}-dien/amine, (ii) Hg^{II}Cl-dien/amine; C. (i) Hg^{II}-dien/amino acid, (ii) Hg^{II}Cl-dien/amino acid. Diethylenetriamine (dien) was considered as the primary ligand and an amine, *i.e.* ethylenediamine (en), 2-amino-ethanol (2-amath), amino acid *i.e.* glycine (gly), L-lysine (lys), L-histidine (hist), DL-alanine (alan), glutamic acid (glu) and L-cysteine (cyst) were considered as the secondary ligand. The stepwise stability constants were evaluated at two different temperatures, *viz.* 30 and 45 $\pm$ 0.01° at 0.1 M ionic strength (with respect to KNO₃). With the help of the stabilities evaluated at two different temperatures, the thermodynamic parameters namely ΔF° , ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated. The titrations have been carried out employing Bjerrum-Calvin's pH-titration technique.

Experimental

Diethylenetriamine (dien) (Pfaltz and Baker) was dried over potassium hydroxide and distilled.